

**D4.1 6G V2X/Digital Twin validation
strategy
v1.0**

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**Programa de Universalización de
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Table of Contents

Table of Contents	3
List of Tables	5
List of Figures	6
Acronyms	7
Executive Summary	8
1 Introduction	9
1.1 Document objectives	9
1.2 Relation to the project's activities	10
1.3 Deliverable overview	10
2 Selected components for demonstration	11
2.1 Tele-operated vehicle	12
2.2 Mobile network	12
2.3 Tele-operation centre	12
3 Automotive testbed setup	13
3.1 5G network	14
3.2 Edge computing facility	15
3.3 Modems and routers	16
3.4 Vehicles and equipment	17
4 Test cases	20
4.1 Test site overview	20
4.2 Testcase 1 – CAVRide testing	20
4.2.1 Test case purpose	20
4.2.2 Test case pre-conditions	21
4.2.3 Equipment involved	21
4.2.4 Test description	21
4.2.5 Measurements collected	22
4.2.6 Test results	22
4.3 Testcase 2 – Performance of QoS prediction for ToD	22
4.3.1 Test case purpose	22
4.3.2 Test case pre-conditions	22

4.3.3	Equipment involved	22
4.3.4	Test description	22
4.3.5	Measurements collected	22
4.3.6	Test results	23
5	Conclusions	24
6	References	25

List of Tables

Table 1. Example of services and scenarios offered by IDIADA testbed..... 14

List of Figures

Figure 1 Implemented architecture.	11
Figure 2 Functional architecture for the demonstrator.	12
Figure 3 CAVRide used as the tele-operated vehicle.	12
Figure 4. IDIADA Connected Vehicle Hub.	13
Figure 5. IDIADA Connected Vehicle Hub - Antennas Sites.	13
Figure 6. Quectel RM500Q-GL modem.	16
Figure 7. Teltonika RUTX50 5G router.	17
Figure 8. CAVRide Architecture.	18
Figure 9 Main track where the ToD use case will be tested.	20

Acronyms

API	Application Programming Interface
AS	Application Server
HDD	Hard Disk Drive
NATing	Network Address Translation
NEF	Network Exposure Function
NR	New Radio
NSA	Non-Stand Alone
NWDAF	Network Data Analytics Function
PLMN	Public Land Mobile Network
PF	Prediction Function
QoS	Quality of Service
RAM	Random-Access Memory
RAT	Inter-Radio Access Technology
SA	Stand-Alone
ToD	Tele-operation Driving
ToC	Tele-operated Centre
ToV	Tele-operate Vehicle
UNICO	Universalización de Infraestructuras Digitales para la Cohesión
V2X	Vehicle to everything
vCPE	virtual Customer Premises Equipment
VLAN	Virtual Local Area Network
VPN	Virtual Private Networks

Executive Summary

This document corresponds to the deliverable "D4.1 – 6G V2X/Digital Twin validation strategy" of the 6GTWINROAD-MNO subproject, "AI/ML driven 6G public networks enabling future V2X services".

This document reports the identified technologies and services that will be used to evaluate the performance of the QoS prediction for tele-operated driving. In addition, it describes the test site where the use case will be evaluated and provides detailed information about the vehicles to be used, the deployed network, and the edge server where the tele-operating application will be running. Finally, the document will present the two testcases that were designed within the project to evaluate the designed technologies and the overall use case.

I

1 Introduction

The aim of 6GTWINROAD-MNO is to design, evaluate, and test a context-aware AI-based architecture beyond 5G. This architecture will enable interaction between the network, its environment, and the Vehicle-to-everything (V2X) applications. It will allow the network to automatically change any parameter to provide seamless and safe experience for vehicle passengers.

In Deliverable D2.1 [1], we identified two use cases to study in 6GTWINROAD-MNO. The first use case is the Quality of Service (QoS) prediction for Tele-operated Driving (ToD), where we will develop an exposure API that will allow the tele-operating centre to be aware of network changes that might impact the behaviour of the ToD. In this way, the remote driver will be able to know about any network problem with time margin to take a decision without risking with an accident or sudden breaking. The second identified use case was the digital twin for cooperative perception, where we will develop an architecture with exposure Application Programming Interface (API) that allows the network to interact with the application and a historical database to enhance the experience of driving when using a connected vehicle. To enable the deployment of the two use cases, we presented in Deliverable D3.2 [2] a preliminary architecture based on 3GPP architecture for 5G Stand-Alone (SA) networks, Open-Radio Access Network (O-RAN) architecture, and exposure API such as CAMARA [3]. As discussed in D2.1 [1], only the first use case will be deployed in real network, whereas the second use case will be evaluated using simulation tools.

In this context, Deliverable D4.1 presents the components required to demonstrate and evaluate the use case of QoS prediction for ToD. These components include the tele-operated vehicle, the network, and the tele-operation centre. All these components will be available in IDIADA Connected Vehicle-Hub (CVH) that will be also described in this document. Finally, the testing plan is formulated as two test cases: tele-operated vehicle performance, and QoS prediction for ToD performance. In the first test case, we will evaluate the performance of ToD when changing network parameters (latency and bandwidth) and driving environment (speed and type of road). In the second test case, we will evaluate the performance of the QoS prediction when one of the cells covering the track will be shut down.

1.1 Document objectives

The Deliverable D4.1 aims at:

- Identifying the component of the use case and testbed that will be used to evaluate the performance of QoS prediction for ToD use case.
- Describing IDIADA CVH where the use case will be evaluated.

- Identifying and describing the test cases that will be used to evaluate the use case.

1.2 Relation to the project's activities

This deliverable is framed within the Work Package 4 of the 6GTWINROAD-MNO project. This Work Package is responsible for validating the selected use cases identified in WP2 and enabled by the 6G V2X technologies developed in WP3.

This deliverable is the output of task T4.1 that is outlined below:

T4.1 Use Case and Technology validation strategy: This task focuses on the definition of the followed strategy to validate the developed 6G V2X technologies. The strategy definition will include:

- Identifying target 6G V2X technologies developed in WP3.
- Define a test site for 6G V2X definition.
- Define a test plan and associated KPIs for the defined validations.

This task will be executed in coordination with T4.2 and T4.3, which will be executed by third parties (IDIADA).

1.3 Deliverable overview

The remainder of this document is structured as follows:

- Section 2 provides a description of the technologies and component that will be used to evaluate the performance of the use case.
- Section 3 provides an overview of used testbed.
- Section 4 describes the test cases designed to evaluate use case performance.
- Section 5 concludes the document.

2 Selected components for demonstration

As described in D2.1 [1], two use cases are considered in this project: Quality of Service (QoS) prediction for Tele-operated driving, and digital twin for cooperative perception. Due to the unavailability of the components needed to deploy use case 2, only the first use case will be deployed. In this context, the architecture in Figure 1 (based on the architecture presented in D3.2 [2]) will be implemented to provide the necessary features to deploy the QoS prediction tools.

Figure 1 Implemented architecture.

In this architecture, the mobile network can be either 2G, 3G, 4G, or 5G Non-Standalone (NSA) network as it will be explained in the next section. As the 5G network is NSA, it does not have a Network Exposure Function (NEF) and Network Data Analytics Function (NWDAF). The latter is normally the function responsible for all data analytics and it is where the Prediction Function (PF) (proposed in D2.1 [1]) should normally be if we have fully deployed 5G SA network. The NEF is responsible of exposing the services of NWDAF to external applications. In addition, the CAMARA like API is developed to provide the network services in a transparent and simple way like what is provided by the CAMARA project [3].

In this project, we are developing an API that emulate these three functions. In particular, all the elements in the functional architecture presented in D2.1 [1] and shown in will be used for the demonstration at the end of the project.

Figure 2 Functional architecture for the demonstrator.

The demonstrator will have the three elements of Figure 2: The Tele-operate Vehicle (ToV), the mobile network, and the Tele-operated Centre (ToC).

2.1 Tele-operated vehicle

The ToV will be the CAVRide provide by IDIADA (Figure 3). It includes a 3G/4G/5G router to connect to the network and the in-Vehicle ToD Interface. It is described in Section 3.4.

Figure 3 CAVRide used as the tele-operated vehicle.

2.2 Mobile network

The network is deployed in IDIADA Connected Vehicle-Hub (CVH) and described in Section 3.1. It also includes the PF that will be implemented as an emulation of the NWDAF as explained above. The PF will get network information from the Operation and Maintenance (O&M) of the IDIADA network through an API that is developed in the project.

2.3 Tele-operation centre

The ToC is already available in IDIADA. It includes the Tele-operation Driving (ToD) Application Server (AS), the ToD interface, and the PF client that were explained in D2.1 [1].

3 Automotive testbed setup

With the aim of replicating many possible network conditions that a vehicle might encounter on the road, the ability to cover test tracks with the full range of access technologies enabling the development and deployment of V2X applications is an important requirement from a network design perspective in 6GTWINROAD-MNO project. This includes a cellular network spanning all generations from 2G to 5G.

For this reason, the 6GTWINROAD-MNO project will test and evaluate the developed use case of QoS prediction for Tele-operated driving [1] and the related technologies in the test site (IDIADA Connected Vehicle-Hub – CVH) in Santa Oliva (near Barcelona), Spain (see Figure 4). The testbed is located on the IDIADA proving ground. It consists of a 5G network (See Section 3.1), an Edge computing facility (See Section 3.2), modems and routers (See Section 3.3), and vehicles and equipment (See Section 3.4).

Figure 4. IDIADA Connected Vehicle Hub.

The proving ground covers an area of 370 hectares and comprises 14 multi-purpose test tracks with a unique, exclusive, and controlled environment capable of reproducing worldwide network configurations and conditions to develop and validate connected vehicle solutions from 2G to 5G Non-Stand Alone (NSA). Full coverage of the proving ground is provided by 4 multi-standard radio base stations (see Figure 5).

Figure 5. IDIADA Connected Vehicle Hub - Antennas Sites.

3.1 5G network

One of the main objectives of the test tracks on the proving ground is to replicate conditions and situations that may occur on the roads of different countries. These capabilities are also reflected in the available mobile communication technologies, as the proving ground is part of a commercial network and offers the possibility to realize services with different situations that could occur in everyday road use. Examples of such services and scenarios are presented in

Table 1.

Table 1. Example of services and scenarios offered by IDIADA testbed.

Type of Service	Basic	All technologies are enabled (2G, 3G, 4G, and 5G NSA) with carrier aggregation for LTE (4G) and NR (5G), MIMO (4x4 → 4G and 8x2 → 5G) and 300 Mbps throughput with 18 ms latency on average.
	Predefined	Intra-site handovers, Inter-site handovers, and Inter-Radio Access Technology (RAT) handovers.
		4G and 5G carrier aggregation with which tests are performed by combining two 4G carriers (1800 MHz and 2100 MHz) or 4G and 5G carriers.
		Variable signal conditions to allow testing under different radio channel quality conditions.
Customized	MIMO test whereby, by changing some features, we are able to test different MIMO configurations (2x2, 2x4, 4x4).	
	IMS voice test whereby customers can test standard IMS voice calls through IDIADA-Orange commercial SIMs.	
		If Basic and Predefined approaches do not fit with client’s requirements, we will analyse and provide, if possible, a tailored solution. This service allows clients to describe the test they wish to perform. When this happens, the Connected Vehicle team has to study if changes are possible and finally confirm the decision to Proving Ground department. Each case must be studied to determine whether it is possible to implement the changes on all tacks.

To meet the test requirements, the test site has an operational network supporting mobile generations from 2G to 5G NSA, with bandwidths similar to those found in public networks.

The 4 base stations consist of a total of 9 sectors (see Figure 5) with the following technologies:

- 2G in 1800 MHz (Bandwidth = 0.2 MHz per sector)
- 3G at 900 MHz (Bandwidth = 5 MHz)
- 4G in 1800 MHz (Bandwidth = 20 MHz) and 2100 MHz (Bandwidth = 10 MHz)
- 5G NSA at 3500 MHz (Bandwidth = 60 MHz)

A dedicated Public Land Mobile Network (PLMN) ID is assigned to testbed users, allowing data to and from the vehicles to be efficiently routed to the on-premises infrastructure and platforms for integrate third party hardware and software testing.

As a connection method, SIM cards from the IDIADA network will be available with different network configurations. Such configurations are divided into cards with RAT limitation (e.g., only 4G connectivity) and cards with throughput limitation (e.g., 150 Mbps limits).

3.2 Edge computing facility

The edge computing facility will provide the environment where the developed application will run and benefit from 5G network connectivity. The purpose of considering 5G edge computing is to process use case data with lowest possible end-to-end latency. Placing this process point in the same premises where the cellular network is located adds the feature of controlled end-to-end path for the services with reduced end-to-end latency, which is mandatory for many automotive use cases. In this section, a deep description of the edge server and relevant info about how to deploy it is provided.

The 5G edge server is a bare metal server, currently running Ubuntu 22.04 as the operating system with Open Stack [4] as virtual infrastructure manager. The features of this server are explained below:

- This server offers virtual machines (VM) that can host the server side of applications of the use case.
- Based on the requirements of the application that is hosted in the VM, the latter can rely on a subset of physical resources (virtual Customer Premises Equipment – vCPE, Random-Access Memory – RAM, Hard Disk Drive – HDD, and networking resources) of the total available in the server. OpenStack is responsible of guaranteeing the availability of resources for the VM and their proper deployment.
- The server can offer virtual switching. Hence VMs can communicate among each other. It can be considered as having multiple applications communicating and contributing for specific outcome.
- The edge server can adapt VMs to communicate with customized network settings. Hence, whatever is needed in terms of network customization like, Virtual Local Area Network (VLAN) tagging, subnet assignment, bridging, Network Address Translation (NATing), tunnelling, Virtual Private Networks (VPNs), packet forwarding, special encryption method, customized routing,

special encapsulation or re-encapsulation, protocol change, and so on, will be possible through this edge infrastructure.

The hardware resources provided with this server are:

- 16 CPU cores (which can be virtually extended to 32),
- 32-64 GB of RAM,
- 1-2 TB of hard disk space.

These physical resources will be distributed between the VMs that will be created according to the specific use case's requirements and challenges.

3.3 Modems and routers

The modems and routers used in this project have two objectives:

- Send and receive data as required by the ToD applications.
- Collect network/modem/edge metrics to better understand measured application-level KPIs.

Two modems/routers have been identified: Quectel RM500Q-GL 5G modem and Teltonika RUTX50 5G router. The selected modems/routers support both 5G NSA and SA technologies.

- The Quectel RM500Q-GL modem (See Figure 6) is a 5G modem that supports several radio bands including N78 band that will be used in the TARGET-X project. It can provide data rates up to 2.5 Gbps in downlink and 900 Mbps in uplink as mentioned in the data sheet [5]. 4x4 and 2x2 MIMO configurations are enabled by this modem. The modem is connected to a laptop through which other network elements can be connected.

Figure 6. Quectel RM500Q-GL modem.

- The Teltonika RUTX50 5G router (see Figure 7), is a modern router designed to work in the automotive sector, as it has many adapters for various types of vehicle compartments. It has a kit consisting of 4 cellular antennas, 2 Wi-Fi antennas and 1 Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) antenna. It supports both 5G NR SA and NSA bands (e.g., N38, N40, N41, N41, N77, N78), 4G bands (LTE-FDD: B1, B3, B5, B7, B8, B20, B28 and LTE-TDD: B38, B40, B41, B42, B43) [6].

Figure 7. Teltonika RUTX50 5G router

3.4 Vehicles and equipment

For the different tests that will be carried out during the project, IDIADA will provide two vehicles to perform the different use cases. The first one will be a connected vehicle, called CAVRide. The CAVRide has been used for other European projects such as C-Mobile [7] and has the following architecture depicted in Figure 8.

Figure 8. CAVRide Architecture.

The CAVRide components are listed below:

- NetGear GS108 Ethernet Switch
- Delta Components Automotive Ethernet Gigabit PoE Switch
- CAM 1-6: Basler ace 2 GigE – a2A1920-51gcBAS
- IBEO: Ibeo LUX (2010) (Laser Scanner – Frontal LIDAR)
- Ouster OS1-64 (Mid-Range High-Resolution Imaging Lidar – Rear LIDAR)
- ARS 408-21 (Long Range Radar Sensor)
- Mobileye 630 (ADAS system camera)
- NVIDIA Drive PX2 (Perception – Autonomous Car Development Platform)
- IDAPT (IDIADA ADAS Platform Tool)
- Laptop/HMI

This vehicle will be used to obtain information from the vehicle sensors (e.g., cameras, LIDARs, radar sensors, etc.) and thus be able to create what the infrastructure needs in the tested use case. In addition, during the course of the project, tele-operated actions will be taken to assess whether a remote driving service can be realised and perfected. The remote driving service is being developed internally at IDIADA and the vehicle is not yet at remotely control commercialisation stage. Regarding the components of the CAVRide, they are currently organized as shown in Figure 8 above but may undergo some changes and updates. In any case, the components necessary to be able to fulfil the project objectives will not be modified.

Another instrumented vehicle with the ability of connecting to the IDIADA private network will be used. It is equipped with the following:

- 5G router
- External mobile antenna(s)
- GNSS antenna
- Laptop/HMI

4 Test cases

This section describes test plan and the test cases that will be carried out during the trials of 6GTWINROAD-MNO.

4.1 Test site overview

The tests will be performed in IDIADA-CVH as explained in Section 3. The main track where the tele-operation driving will be conducted is depicted in Figure 9.

Figure 9 Main track where the ToD use case will be tested.

The track is covered by two cells: the red zone belongs to cell 1 (Control Tower S2) and green zone belongs to cell 2 (East Curve S2). The yellow zone in the figure is the HO zone. Any cell can be switched off, when necessary, in order to demonstrate the case where the service is down in one cell.

Two test cases will be conducted: CAVRide testing and Performance of QoS prediction for ToD.

4.2 Testcase 1 – CAVRide testing

4.2.1 Test case purpose

The objective of this test is to evaluate the performance of the CAVRide remote driving system in terms of response time for braking and steering:

1. Test the **ideal performance** of the CAVRIDE when the network is setup with normal configuration

2. Provide a **mapping** between the driving environment (speed and road type – curves or straight) and service KPIs (reaction time on breaking and wheel steering) from one side, and required latency, bandwidth, etc. by changing network configuration and uplink video streaming quality

4.2.2 Test case pre-conditions

CAVRide and 5G network fully functional, track reserved for the tests, and tele-operating driver is ready behind the remote station.

4.2.3 Equipment involved

In this testcase, three components are needed: the CAVRide, the mobile network, and the remote station.

4.2.4 Test description

To carry out the test case, the following tasks must be performed:

1. Test ideal scenario
 - Car speed: 20 km/h
 - Network configuration: Normal
 - Path: cell 1 -> cell 2 with no curves
 - Number of measurements: 10
2. Test mapping on straight lane with 20 Km/h (Latency case)
 - Car speed: 20 km/h
 - Network configuration: Add a fixed latency of 25, 50, 100 ms
 - Path: cell 1 -> cell 2 with no curves
 - Number of measurements: 10
3. Test mapping on straight lane with 20 Km/h (video bandwidth case)
 - Car speed: 20 km/h
 - Network configuration: reduce video bandwidth to the half
 - Path: cell 1 -> cell 2 with no curves
 - Number of measurements: 10
4. Test mapping on straight lane with 40 Km/h (Latency case)
 - Car speed: 40 km/h
 - Network configuration: Add a fixed latency of 25, 50, 100 ms
 - Path: cell 1 -> cell 2 with no curves
 - Number of measurements: 10
5. Test mapping on straight lane with 40 Km/h (video bandwidth case)
 - Car speed: 40 km/h
 - Network configuration: reduce video bandwidth to the half
 - Path: cell 1 -> cell 2 with no curves
 - Number of measurements: 10
6. Test mapping on the round-about
 - Same tasks as for the straight lane

4.2.5 Measurements collected

The data collected during the execution of this test case are the following:

- GPS data
- Latency
- Data-Rate
- Velocity
- Breaking reaction time
- Steering reaction time

4.2.6 Test results

The results for each task will be collected in a matrix containing all the results of at least 10 measurements.

4.3 Testcase 2 – Performance of QoS prediction for ToD

4.3.1 Test case purpose

The objective of this test is to test the functionality of the QoS prediction framework.

4.3.2 Test case pre-conditions

CAVRide, connected vehicle, and 5G network fully functional; track reserved for the tests, and tele-operating driver is ready behind the remote station.

4.3.3 Equipment involved

In this testcase, four components are needed: the CAVRide, a connected vehicle, the mobile network, and the remote station.

4.3.4 Test description

To carry out the test case, the following tasks must be performed:

1. Test the collection of information (**cell status**) from **network dashboard** and show it in an excel sheet in the server
2. Test the collection of information (**latency, throughput, RSRP, RSRQ, cellID**) from **the CAVRID and connected vehicle** and show it in an excel sheet in the server
3. Test the **output of the QoS prediction algorithm** when the cell is turned off

4.3.5 Measurements collected

The data collected during the execution of this test case are the following:

- GPS data
- Latency
- Data-Rate
- Velocity

- Breaking reaction time
- Steering reaction time
- Time to break (the time between the notification and the actual the loose of connection)

4.3.6 Test results

The results for each task will be collected in a matrix containing all the results of at least 10 measurements.

5 Conclusions

In this deliverable, we presented the technologies and the components that will be used to evaluate the performance of the QoS prediction for ToD use case. The latter will be evaluated in IDIADA CVH test site that is described in this document. In order to evaluate the performance of the use case, we divided the test plan into two test cases: evaluate the performance of the ToD under different conditions in order to assess the requirements that we need to have a real network to operate ToD, and evaluate the performance of the QoS prediction framework that will reduce the risk of sudden breaking and accident by providing information about network performance degradation to the ToD application.

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